

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857612.

“Integration of Geodetic and imaging Techniques for monitoring and modelling the Earth's surface deformations and Seismic risk – GATHERS”

1st GATHERS workshop **Ignacy Historic Mine, Rybnik, Poland**

22nd September 2022

Preliminary program

16:00-18:00 Workshop

- 16:00-16:15 „*High-rate GNSS: application to mining tremors*”, Iwona Kudłacik (UPWr, Poland)
- 16:15-16:30 „*Integration of GNSS and 5G for precise positioning*”, Chiara Pileggi and Marianna Alghisi (Politecnico di Milano, Italy)
- 16:30-16:45 „*Integration of GNSS and InSAR observations for monitoring deformation of mining areas*”, Damian Tondaś (UPWr, Poland)
- 16:45-17:00 „*Combined DInSAR-PSI approach for deformation map estimation in the area of underground coal mining exploitation*”, Natalia Wielgocka (UPWr, Poland)
- 17:00-17:15 „*Remote Sensing approaches for land use/land cover change detection in coastal areas and oceanic islands: A Review*”, Rafaela Tiengo (cE3c: Centre for Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Changes & Azorean biodiversity group, Portugal)
- 17:15-17:30 „*Instance segmentation of individual grains from a terrestrial laser scanning point cloud of a river bed*”, Agata Walicka (UPWr, Poland)
- 17:30-17:45 „*UAV-based laser scanning for the applications in agriculture and deformation monitoring*”, Ansgar Dreier (University of Bonn, Germany)
- 17:45-18:00 „*Adjustment of ULS strips collected with Velodyne VLP-16 laser scanner*”, Grzegorz Józków (UPWr, Poland)

18:00-21:00 Gala dinner

HR EXCELLENCE IN RESEARCH

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